

Agosto 2022

Herpetologia Brasileira

volume 11 número 2
ISSN: 2316-4670

First record of predation of the leopard tree frog *Boana pardalis* (Anura: Hylidae) by the water snake *Erythrolamprus miliaris* (Squamata: Dipsadidae)

Lucas J. A. O. S. Ferreira*, Elsie Laura Rotenberg, Edelcio Muscat, Matheus de Toledo Moroti.

Projeto Dacnis. Estrada do Rio Escuro, 4754, Sertão das Cotias, 11680-000 Ubatuba, São Paulo, Brazil.

*Corresponding author. E-mail: lucasaosf@gmail.com

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6867850](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6867850)

Feeding is one of the key components in snake natural history, directly influencing activity periods, behavior, and habitat use (Toft, 1985). Snakes can be considered the main predators of anurans, which are an important food source for the group (Vitt, 1983; Vitt & Vangilder, 1983; Sazima & Haddad, 1992; Strüßmann & Sazima, 1993; Toledo et al., 2007). Factors such as the gregarious behavior of anurans during reproductive periods (greater food availability for their predators) may be responsible for this (Wells, 2007).

The water snake *Erythrolamprus miliaris* (Linnaeus, 1758) is a generalist feeder. Prey recorded for it include small mammals, reptiles, and fish, but overwhelmingly amphibians, mostly Hylidae, which comprise 77% of listed prey (van den Burg, 2020). There are also reports of necrophagy (Sazima & Strüßmann, 1990; Gomes et al.,

2017). *Erythrolamprus miliaris* is often found near water bodies, habitat used by many anurans during their reproductive season (Sazima & Haddad, 1992; Marques & Sazima, 2004).

On 5 October 2020, during routine fauna monitoring at 19:53 h, we observed a predation event on a small, muddy streambank located in a study area of the NGO Projeto Dacnis (22°53'44,7" S, 45°56'29,4" W), in the sub-district of São Francisco Xavier, municipality of São José dos Campos, state of São Paulo, Brazil. The snake had already begun ingesting its prey, an adult leopard tree frog *Boana pardalis* (Spix, 1824), by the head (Fig. 1A–1B). The anuran was moving its hind legs, and inflating its body to try to escape the snake's grasp, but its efforts were unsuccessful. From the time we arrived, the snake completely ingested the frog in 10 minutes (Fig. 1C–D).

This event includes another novelty: it is the first report of the defense mechanism of body inflation in *B. pardalis*. The mechanism's purpose is to enlarge the body, making capture and/or ingestion by a predator more difficult (Toledo et al., 2007; Caro, 2014). Six types of defense mechanisms have been reported for Hylidae (Alves et al., 2018), but puffing up the body (*sensu* Toledo et al., 2011) in the leopard tree frog had not been recorded until now.

Boana pardalis is considered a large anuran (Rocha-Lima et al., 2018), and body inflation could pose a problem for *E. miliaris*. It is an aglyphous snake with undifferentiated dentition (isodonty) (Guedes et al., 2018), and does not have elongated posterior teeth to perforate an inflated frog's body as does *Xenodon merremii* (Wagler, 1824). *Xenodon merremii* is also aglyphous, but has differentiated dentition (heterodonty) (Amaral, 1934; Vanzolini et al., 1980; Duellman & Trueb, 1994; Jordão, 1996; Greene, 1997; Guedes et al., 2018) that facilitates puncturing inflated prey. Nonetheless, despite the predator/prey size ratio, inflated prey body, and the lack of differentiated teeth, *E. miliaris* was successful in its predation.

The defensive repertoire of a species or population may have evolved due to the constant and intense pressure exerted by its natural predators (Greene, 1997; Vamosi, 2005; Toledo et al.,

2007). Conversely, predators may also have evolved to suppress antipredation mechanisms, generating cycles in which one evolves to overcome the other's adaptation (Brodie & Brodie, 1999a,b; Geffeney et al., 2002; Toledo et al., 2007). Therefore, the maintenance of a specific defensive behavior theoretically depends on its contribution to the species' survival (Greene, 1988). Likewise, a successful predation strategy means that the predator overcame its prey's defensive mechanisms (e.g., Muscat & Moroti, 2018).

Although predation events are seldom observed (Pombal, 2007), the number of records has increased recently. For *E. miliaris*, despite the significant variety of reported prey, its wide distribution range and shortage of records suggest that many prey species are as yet unknown (van den Burg & Miguel, 2020). We can now include *Boana pardalis* on this list, highlighting the snake's feeding success while lacking any morphological adaptation to counter the frog's inflation defense mechanism.

REFERENCES

Alves I.A.M., Zocca C., Ferreira R.B. 2018. Diversidade de Mecanismo Antipredação de Anfíbios Anuros na Presença de Serpentes. Anais do VII Simpósio sobre a Biodiversidade da Mata Atlântica – Santa Teresa/ES - 07 a 10 de junho de 2018.

- Amaral A. 1934. Curiosos hábitos e particularidades da boipeva (*Xenodon merremii*: Colubridae). *Boletim Biológico* 2:1–3.
- Brodie III E.D., Brodie Jr E.D. 1999a. Costs of exploiting poisonous prey: evolutionary trade-offs in a predator–prey arms race. *Evolution* 53:626–631. DOI:[10.1111/j.1558-5646.1999.tb03798](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.1999.tb03798).
- Brodie E.D., Brodie Jr. E.D. 1999b. Predator–prey arms races. Asymmetrical selection on predators and prey may be reduced when prey are dangerous. *BioScience* 49:557–568. DOI:[10.2307/1313476](https://doi.org/10.2307/1313476)
- Caro T. 2014. Antipredator deception in terrestrial vertebrates. *Current Zoology* 60:16–25. DOI: [10.1093/czoolo/60.1.16](https://doi.org/10.1093/czoolo/60.1.16)
- Duellman W.E., Trueb L. 1994. Biology of amphibians. Johns Hopkins University Press, Baltimore.
- Geffeney S., Brodie Jr., E.D., Brodie III, E.D. 2002. Mechanisms of adaptation in a predator–prey arms race: TTX-resistant sodium channels. *Science* 297:1336–1339. DOI: [10.1126/science.1074310](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1074310)
- Gomes D.F., Gonzalez R.C., Silva-Soares T. 2017. *Erythrolamprus miliaris* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Serpentes: Dipsadidae): report on an unusual event of necrophagy. *Herpetology Notes* 10:417–419.
- Greene H.W. 1988. Antipredator mechanisms in reptiles. Pp. 1–152, in Gans C., Huey R.B. (Eds.), *Biology of the Reptilia. Ecology B: Defense and life history* (Vol. 16). Branta Books, Ann Arbor.
- Greene H.W. 1997. *Snakes: The evolution of mystery in nature*. University of California Press, Berkeley.
- Guedes T.B., Sazima I., Marques O.A. 2018. Does swallowing a toad require any specialisation? Feeding behaviour of the dipsadid snake *Philodryas nattereri* on the bufonid toad *Rhinella jimi*. *Herpetology Notes* 11:825–828.
- Jordão R.S. 1996. Estudo comparativo da alimentação e reprodução de *Waglerophis merremii* e *Xenodon neuwiedii* (Serpentes, Colubridae). MSc. Dissertation, Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil.
- Marques O.A.V., Sazima I. 2004. História natural dos répteis da Estação Ecológica Juréia-Itatins. Pp. 257–277, in Marques O.A., Duleba W. (eds), *Estação Ecológica Juréia-Itatins: Ambiente Físico, Flora e Fauna*. Holos Editora, Ribeirão Preto.

- Muscat E., Moroti M.T. 2018. Predation of *Rhinella ornata* (Anura: Bufonidae) by the water snake *Erythrolamprus miliaris* (Squamata: Dipsadidae) in São Paulo, Brazil. *Herpetology Notes* 11:449–450.
- Pombal Jr. J.P. 2007. Notas sobre predação em uma taxocenose de anfíbios anuros no sudeste do Brasil. *Revista Brasileira de Zoologia* 24:841–843.
- Rocha-Lima A.B.C., Santos I., Duarte L.S.C., Costa W.P. 2018. *Erythrolamprus miliaris orinus* (Reptilia, Squamata, Dipsadidae): tentativas de predação de *Boana faber* e *Leptodactylus latrans*. *Boletim do Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi Ciências Naturais* 13:455–460.
- Sazima I., Haddad C.F.B. 1992. Répteis da Serra do Japi: notas sobre história natural. Pp. 212–231, in Morellato L.P.C. (ed.), *História Natural da Serra do Japi*, Editora da Unicamp, Campinas.
- Sazima I., Strüssmann C. 1990. Necrofagia em serpentes brasileiras: exemplos e Previsões. *Revista Brasileira de Biologia* 50:463–468.
- Strüssmann C., Sazima I. 1993. The snake assemblage of the Pantanal at Poconé, western Brazil: faunal composition and ecological summary. *Studies on Neotropical Fauna and Environmental* 28:157–168. DOI: [10.1080/01650529309360900](https://doi.org/10.1080/01650529309360900).
- Toft C.A. 1985. Resource partitioning in amphibians and reptiles. *Copeia* 1985:1–21. DOI: [10.2307/1444785](https://doi.org/10.2307/1444785)
- Toledo L.F., Ribeiro R.S., Haddad C.F.B. 2007. Anurans as prey: an exploratory analysis and size relationships between predators and their prey. *Journal of Zoology* 271:170–177. DOI: [10.1111/j.1469-7998.2006.00195.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7998.2006.00195.x)
- Toledo, L.F., Sazima, I., Haddad, C. F. B. 2011. Behavioral defenses of anurans: an overview. *Ethology Ecology & Evolution* 23:1–25. DOI: [10.1080/03949370.2010.534321](https://doi.org/10.1080/03949370.2010.534321)
- Vamosi S.M. 2005. On the role of enemies in divergence and diversification of prey: a review and synthesis. *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 83:894–910. DOI: [10.1139/z05-063](https://doi.org/10.1139/z05-063)
- Vanzolini P.E., Ramos-Costa A.M.M., Vitt L.J. 1980. Répteis das Caatingas. Rio de Janeiro, Academia Brasileira de Ciências.
- van den Burg M.P. 2020. How to source and collate natural history information: a case study of reported prey items of *Erythrolamprus miliaris* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Herpetology Notes* 13:739–746.
- van den Burg M.P., Miguel I. 2020. Report of new predator-prey interactions

of *Erythrolamprus miliaris* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Herpetology Notes* 13:361–363.

Vitt L.J. 1983. Ecology of an anuran-eating guild of terrestrial tropical snakes. *Herpetologica* 39:52–66.

Vitt L.J., Vangilder L.D. 1983. Ecology of a snake community in northeastern Brazil. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 4:273–296.

Wells K.D. 2007. The ecology and behavior of amphibians. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.

Editor: H. C. Costa

Figure 1. Erythrolamprus miliaris preying on *Boana pardalis*. The snake began ingestion from the head (A and B), then the body (C), and after approximately 10 minutes, ingested the prey completely (D). The predation event took place in a stream in an open area, in São Francisco Xavier, state of São Paulo, on 5 October 2020 at 19:53. *Boana pardalis* was calling in the same environment at night. Photos: Matheus T. Moroti.